

Appendix E: Additional figures

Fig. E.2. Spectral window function of the CARMENES RV time series. See Sect. 2.1.

Fig. E.3. TESS target pixel file (TFP) of KOBE-1 for sectors 17 (*upper panel*) and 57 (*bottom panel*) using the `tpfplotter` algorithm. The white cross represents the position of the target, while the red dots are objects in the field detected by *Gaia* with $\Delta G < 8$ mag. SPOC aperture is shown as red squares. See Sect. 2.3.

Fig. E.4. Nearby sources contributing to the TESS photometry of KOBE-1. *Top:* Heatmap with the pixel-by-pixel flux fraction from KOBE-1 in sector 17. The red grid is the SPOC aperture. The pixel scale is $21 \text{ arcsec pixel}^{-1}$. The small-white dots represent all the *Gaia* sources, and the two sources that most contribute to the aperture flux are highlighted in purple and green as shown in the legend. The areas of the dots scale with the emitted fluxes. *Bottom:* Pie chart showing the flux contributions to the SPOC aperture. This plot has been generated with `tess-cont`. See Sect. 2.3.

Fig. E.5. *Top:* ASAS-SN photometric time series of KOBE-1. *Left:* GLS periodograms of the ASAS-SN photometry corrected for a long-term linear trend. The vertical dashed lines indicate the lunar synodic (black) and sidereal (grey) month. The horizontal dotted lines indicate the 10% (orange), 1% (blue), and 0.1% (green) FAP levels. *Right:* Phase-folded light curves to the maximum power period obtained by the GLS periodogram (indicated with a red dot). The gray data points correspond to a 2.5-day binning. See Sect. 2.3.

Fig. E.6. Corner plot for the preferred RV model (2p1c2c, two planets in circular orbits). See Sect. 4.1.2.

Fig. E.7. Correlation for the RV residuals (after subtracting planet b in the *left* column, planet c in the *middle*, and both planets in the *right*) with the activity indicators. Blue line is the linear regression, and in the grey box are shown the correlation coefficients (R from Pearson, and ρ from Spearman). See Sect. 4.1.2.

Fig. E.8. *Top:* CaIRT₂ measurements (colored dots) with the GP model (red line) and the 68.7% and 95% confidence intervals (dark and light grey regions). *Bottom:* Residuals of the GP model. See Sect. 4.1.2.

Fig. E.9. TESS light curves for KOBE-1, including the second half of sector 17 (*upper panel*) and sector 57 (two *lower panels*). Each panel shows the different time series for each sector before and after the down-link gap. See caption from Fig. 4 (Sect. 4.2) for further details.